

Title: Real-World Safety Profile of Xanomeline-Tropium (Cobenfy), the First Muscarinic Agonist Antipsychotic: A Disproportionality Analysis of the FDA Adverse Event Reporting System

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Abstract

Background and Hypothesis

Xanomeline-tropium (Cobenfy), the first non-dopaminergic antipsychotic approved in over 30 years, received FDA approval for schizophrenia in September 2024. We hypothesized that its muscarinic M1/M4 agonist mechanism produces a safety profile characterized by gastrointestinal and cholinergic adverse events, with reduced metabolic and extrapyramidal burden compared with D2 antagonists.

Study Design

We conducted a disproportionality analysis of the FDA Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS) from Q4 2024 to Q4 2025. Signals were identified using a four-method battery (reporting odds ratio [ROR], proportional reporting ratio, information component, empirical Bayesian geometric mean), with consensus defined as positivity on three or more methods. Active-comparator analyses compared xanomeline-tropium against six D2 antagonists using Bonferroni-corrected ROR.

Study Results

Among 1,808,859 deduplicated cases, 1,423 listed xanomeline-tropium as suspect. We identified 56 consensus signals, of which 37 were pharmacological. Dominant signals were gastrointestinal (nausea, ROR 7.5; vomiting, 8.4; constipation, 6.5) and muscarinic/anticholinergic (urinary retention, 44.0; drooling, 61.0). In active-comparator analyses, weight gain (ROR vs olanzapine: 0.11) and extrapyramidal symptoms were significantly lower versus all comparators, while gastrointestinal events were significantly higher. All major events were early-onset (median 0-3 days). E-values indicated that 46 of 56 signals were robust to unmeasured confounding.

Conclusions

The post-marketing safety profile of xanomeline-trospium confirms a predominantly gastrointestinal and cholinergic adverse event burden with markedly lower metabolic and extrapyramidal reporting relative to D2 antagonists. Drooling and urinary retention warrant targeted monitoring during treatment initiation.

Keywords: pharmacovigilance, disproportionality analysis, schizophrenia, muscarinic agonist, active comparator, adverse drug reaction

Introduction

The pharmacological treatment of schizophrenia has been dominated by dopamine D2 receptor antagonism since the introduction of chlorpromazine in 1954. Despite incremental improvements through first- and second-generation antipsychotics, the core mechanism has remained unchanged, and the class-wide burden of metabolic syndrome, weight gain, extrapyramidal symptoms (EPS), and hyperprolactinemia continues to drive nonadherence and long-term morbidity.^{1,2} The approval of xanomeline-trospium (Cobenfy; Bristol-Myers Squibb) by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) on September 26, 2024, for the treatment of schizophrenia in adults broke a 30-year dependence on D2 antagonism as the sole antipsychotic mechanism.^{3,4}

Xanomeline is a muscarinic M1/M4 receptor agonist originally investigated for Alzheimer disease, where its development was abandoned due to dose-limiting cholinergic adverse effects, particularly gastrointestinal and cardiovascular events.⁵ The combination with trospium chloride, a peripherally acting muscarinic antagonist that does not cross the blood-brain barrier, was designed to mitigate peripheral cholinergic toxicity while preserving central muscarinic agonism.⁶ The EMERGENT-1 (phase 2), EMERGENT-2, and EMERGENT-3 (phase 3) trials demonstrated efficacy on the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS), with a safety profile characterized primarily by nausea, vomiting, dyspepsia, and constipation, and low rates of weight gain and EPS.⁶⁻⁸

However, the controlled trial populations (total n=690 across three placebo-controlled trials) may not fully reflect the safety profile in broader clinical use, where patients have greater comorbidity, polypharmacy, and demographic heterogeneity. Spontaneous adverse event reporting systems such as the FAERS provide a complementary source of post-marketing surveillance, enabling hypothesis-generating signal detection through disproportionality analysis.⁹⁻¹¹ A recent FAERS analysis by Song et al.¹² examined 1,142 reports

through Q3 2025 using three disproportionality methods, confirming gastrointestinal and urinary signals but without active-comparator analyses, E-values, or systematic classification of signals as drug effects versus disease manifestations.

Here we report a four-method disproportionality analysis of FAERS data spanning five quarters after FDA approval, with head-to-head comparisons against six D2 antagonists, Weibull time-to-onset modeling, and E-value sensitivity analysis.

Methods

Study Design and Data Source

We conducted a retrospective pharmacovigilance study using FAERS quarterly data files (ASCII format) from Q4 2024 through Q4 2025, representing approximately 14 months of post-marketing exposure. FAERS quarterly files use the Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities (MedDRA) for coding adverse events as preferred terms (PTs). The study was pre-registered on the Open Science Framework prior to any FAERS queries (doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/2PWUD), including prespecified hypotheses, PT lists, signal detection thresholds, and analysis plans. Reporting follows the READUS-PV guideline for disproportionality analyses using pharmacovigilance databases.¹³

Data Processing

FAERS quarterly ASCII files were downloaded from the FDA public dashboard, loaded into a DuckDB analytical database, and deduplicated by case identifier (CASEID), retaining the most recent version of each report. Drug names were standardized to active ingredient level using RxNorm mapping, with xanomeline-trospium identified through six name variants (including “COBENFY,” “KARXT,” “XANOMELINE AND TROSPIUM CHLORIDE,” and related spellings). Active comparators were olanzapine, risperidone, aripiprazole, quetiapine, lurasidone, and brexpiprazole, each similarly standardized.

Case Identification

Cases were identified as any report listing xanomeline-trospium as a primary suspect (PS) or secondary suspect (SS) drug. Comparator cases were identified analogously. Demographic, reaction, outcome, indication, and therapy data were extracted and linked by primary identifier.

Disproportionality Analysis

For each drug-PT pair with three or more reports, we computed four standard disproportionality measures with a 0.5 continuity correction applied to all 2x2 cell counts:

1. **Reporting odds ratio (ROR)** with 95% confidence interval (CI); signal threshold: lower 95% CI > 1.
2. **Proportional reporting ratio (PRR)**; signal threshold: PRR \geq 2, chi-squared \geq 4.
3. **Empirical Bayesian Geometric Mean (EBGM)** from a multi-item gamma-Poisson shrinker (MGPS) model fitted to the full FAERS database; signal threshold: EB05 (lower 5th percentile) \geq 2.
4. **Information component (IC)** from Bayesian confidence propagation neural network; signal threshold: IC025 (lower 95% credible interval) > 0.

Consensus signals were defined as positivity on three or more of four methods.^{14,15} Benjamini-Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) correction was applied to ROR p-values; the remaining three methods incorporate Bayesian shrinkage or alternative thresholds that inherently penalize sparse data. All ROR p-values for consensus signals were <0.0001 after FDR correction.

Active-Comparator Analysis

For 32 prespecified PTs across six comparators (192 comparisons), we computed the ROR of xanomeline-trospium versus each comparator within a 2x2 framework restricted to cases of either drug. Bonferroni correction was applied ($\alpha = 0.05/192 = 0.00026$). Age-sex adjusted estimates were computed using the Mantel-Haenszel (MH) method stratified by age group (<40, 40-64, \geq 65 years) and sex, with Robins-Breslow-Greenland variance estimation. Brexpiprazole comparisons should be interpreted cautiously given its older patient population (median age 68 years vs 40 years for xanomeline-trospium), which may reflect different indication patterns.

Time-to-Onset Analysis

For PTs with 20 or more reports containing valid therapy start and event onset dates, time-to-onset (TTO) was computed in days. Weibull distributions were fitted, with the shape parameter (beta) indicating early-onset with decreasing hazard ($\beta < 1$), constant hazard ($\beta = 1$), or late-onset with increasing hazard ($\beta > 1$).

Sensitivity and Validation Analyses

Pre-registered sensitivity analyses included: (1) restriction to primary suspect reports only; (2) restriction to US reports only; (3) restriction to healthcare professional (HCP) reporters; and (4) Weber effect assessment by quarterly report counts. Additional post-hoc sensitivity analyses, not specified in the pre-registration, included: (5) restriction to reports with serious outcomes (death, hospitalization, life-threatening events, disability); and (6) exclusion of cases with concomitant antipsychotic medication. Post-hoc validation analyses included E-values for unmeasured confounding,¹⁶ sex- and age-stratified disproportionality, sequential (quarter-by-quarter cumulative) signal detection, signal masking analysis, positive and negative control drug-event pairs, label concordance with the FDA prescribing information,¹⁷ reporter-stratified (HCP versus consumer) ROR comparison, and indication-restricted analysis (schizophrenia cases only).

Signal Classification

Consensus signals were classified as either pharmacological (plausibly attributable to drug mechanism) or disease manifestation (attributable to the underlying condition of schizophrenia or psychiatric comorbidity) based on clinical review. PTs reflecting core symptoms of psychosis (hallucinations, delusions, paranoia), behavioral disturbance (aggression, agitation), or substance use comorbidity were classified as disease manifestations. Without this classification, the schizophrenia indication confounds interpretation: a high ROR for “psychotic disorder” more likely reflects disease worsening or treatment failure than a pharmacological adverse effect.

Software

All analyses were performed in Python 3.10+ using DuckDB 1.5, pandas, NumPy, and SciPy. Code is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19623168>.

Results

Study Population

After deduplication, the FAERS database contained 1,808,859 unique cases across five quarterly files (Q4 2024 to Q4 2025). We identified 1,423 cases listing xanomeline-trospium as a suspect drug (eFigure 3). Active comparator case counts were: quetiapine 9,074; olanzapine 6,926; risperidone 6,254; aripiprazole 5,516; brexpiprazole 1,288; and lurasidone 806.

Xanomeline-trospium cases had a median age of 40 years (IQR 30-51; age available in 752 [52.8%] reports), with 442 (31.1%) female, 656 (46.1%) male, and 325 (22.8%) sex not reported (Table 1). US reports constituted 98.9% of cases. Healthcare professionals submitted 47.3% of reports, compared with 57%-71% for comparators except lurasidone (44.2%).

Primary Disproportionality Analysis

Among 148 drug-PT pairs meeting the minimum threshold of three reports, 56 reached consensus signal status (positivity on ≥ 3 of 4 methods), of which 39 were positive on all four methods (Table 2). After clinical classification, 37 signals were pharmacological and 19 were disease manifestations (Figure 1).

Gastrointestinal signals constituted the dominant cluster, with 12 of 14 gastrointestinal PTs reaching signal status. The five highest-volume pharmacological signals were nausea (n=314; ROR 7.5 [95% CI 6.7-8.6]), vomiting (n=239; 8.4 [7.3-9.7]), constipation (n=110; 6.5 [5.3-7.8]), dyspepsia (n=51; 7.2 [5.4-9.5]), and gastroesophageal reflux disease (n=36; 6.2 [4.5-8.7]).

Muscarinic/anticholinergic signals were prominent, reflecting the dual agonist-antagonist pharmacology. Urinary retention was the second-strongest pharmacological signal (n=92; ROR 44.0 [35.5-54.5]), followed by drooling (n=30; 61.0 [42.3-88.0]), dry mouth (n=35; 6.2 [4.4-8.7]), salivary hypersecretion (n=15; 23.8 [14.3-39.4]), anuria (n=3; 8.1 [2.8-23.1]), and dysuria (n=16; 7.6 [4.7-12.3]). The paradoxical co-occurrence of both drooling and dry mouth is pharmacologically consistent with central M1 agonism (promoting salivation) competing with peripheral M3 antagonism by trospium.

Cardiovascular signals included tachycardia (n=22; ROR 3.9 [2.6-5.9]) and heart rate increased (n=24; 3.7 [2.5-5.6]). Contrary to our pre-registered hypothesis (H2), hypertension did not reach signal status.

Neurological signals included vision blurred (n=50; 5.6 [4.3-7.5]), hyperhidrosis (n=46; 6.5 [4.9-8.8]), tremor (n=23; 2.6 [1.7-3.9]), and somnolence (n=32; 2.6 [1.8-3.7]). Akathisia was detected as a signal (n=7; ROR 10.4 [5.1-21.4]), although the active-comparator analysis demonstrated significantly lower reporting relative to all D2 antagonists – suggesting this signal reflects background reporting rather than a drug-specific effect.

Notably absent signals included weight gain (n=10; ROR 0.6, no signal), hyperglycemia (n=0), diabetes mellitus (n=0), metabolic syndrome (n=0), dyslipidemia (n=0), tardive dyskinesia (n=1), hyperprolactinemia (n=0), and QT prolongation (n=0).

Active-Comparator Analysis

Across 192 pairwise comparisons (32 PTs x 6 comparators), 79 were Bonferroni-significant (Figure 2; Table 3). The results demonstrated a consistent mechanistic divergence:

- **Gastrointestinal events were significantly higher** for xanomeline-trospium versus all six comparators for nausea (ROR range 3.9-26.8), vomiting (2.3-20.7), and constipation (2.3-43.3). The extreme values in the brexpiprazole comparison (constipation ROR 43.3) reflect the small denominator for that comparator (n=1,288) and the different age and indication mix.
- **Metabolic events were significantly lower:** weight gain was reduced versus olanzapine (ROR 0.11 [0.06-0.21]), risperidone (0.10 [0.06-0.19]), aripiprazole (0.10 [0.06-0.21]), quetiapine (0.10 [0.06-0.18]), and brexpiprazole (0.14 [0.06-0.36]); all Bonferroni-significant.
- **EPS were significantly lower:** akathisia was reduced versus olanzapine (ROR 0.19), risperidone (0.22), aripiprazole (0.12), and brexpiprazole (0.17). Dystonia, parkinsonism, and extrapyramidal disorder showed consistent reductions.
- **Somnolence and sedation were significantly lower** versus olanzapine, risperidone, aripiprazole, and quetiapine.
- **Anticholinergic events were significantly higher:** urinary retention was elevated versus all comparators (ROR range 3.7-6.8), and dry mouth versus four of six comparators.

MH age-sex adjusted analyses were directionally consistent with crude results. Of 108 evaluable comparisons, no MH-adjusted ROR reversed direction compared with the crude estimate, though some comparisons lost Bonferroni significance due to sparse strata reducing precision (eTable 15).

Time-to-Onset Analysis

Seven PTs met the threshold for Weibull fitting (≥ 20 reports with valid dates; eTable 40). All showed early-onset patterns with Weibull shape parameters below 1 (range 0.56-0.91), indicating decreasing hazard after initial exposure (eFigure 5). Median TTO was 0-3 days across all events. Urinary retention had the shortest onset (median 0 days, $\beta = 0.91$), while vomiting had the longest tail (median 2 days, $\beta = 0.59$).

Label Concordance

Of 21 PTs listed in the FDA prescribing information,¹⁷ 18 were testable in FAERS (≥ 3 reports). Of these, 9 were concordant (detected as FAERS signals), yielding a label sensitivity of 50% (eFigure 6). Concordant PTs included nausea, vomiting, constipation, dyspepsia, tachycardia, heart rate increased, somnolence,

gastroesophageal reflux disease, and urinary retention. Label PTs not reaching signal status included hypertension, diarrhea, headache, dizziness, weight increased, abdominal distension, angioedema, and seizure.

Among the 47 signals not in the prescribing information, 19 were classified as disease manifestations of schizophrenia (eg, hallucinations, psychotic disorder, paranoia). The remaining 28 novel pharmacological signals included drooling (ROR 61.0), salivary hypersecretion (23.8), dry mouth (6.2), hyperhidrosis (6.5), vision blurred (5.6), akathisia (10.4), and treatment noncompliance (7.0).

Sensitivity Analyses

Primary disproportionality results were consistent across all sensitivity analyses (eTable 39):

- **Primary suspect only:** 56 signals (identical to primary analysis).
- **US reports only:** 62 signals (consistent; slight increase due to more homogeneous denominator).
- **HCP reporters only:** 41 of 56 signals retained (73%); reduction attributable to smaller sample size (n=706) rather than qualitative signal loss.
- **Serious outcomes only:** 14 signals retained among 131 serious cases; core GI signals (nausea, vomiting, constipation) and urinary retention persisted.
- **Polypharmacy excluded:** After removing 125 cases (8.8%) with concomitant antipsychotics – most commonly clozapine (n=45), olanzapine (n=26), and risperidone (n=24) – 53 of 56 signals were retained. Drooling ROR changed minimally (61.0 to 60.0; -1.6%), confirming this signal is not confounded by clozapine co-prescription.¹⁸
- **Reporter-stratified:** Core pharmacological signals (nausea, vomiting, constipation, urinary retention, drooling) were consistent between HCP and consumer reporters, with ROR ratios near 1.0.
- **Weber effect:** Quarterly xanomeline-trospium reports increased by approximately 34 per quarter across the study period, with no evidence of reporting decay.

E-Value Analysis

E-values quantified robustness to unmeasured confounding: 46 of 56 consensus signals had E-value lower CI ≥ 3.0 , indicating that an unmeasured confounder would need to be associated with both the drug and the outcome by at least a factor of 3 to explain away these signals. The strongest signals (drooling, E-value CI 84.0; urinary retention, 70.6; vomiting, 14.2) were highly resistant to confounding (eTable 30).

Sequential Signal Detection

Cumulative quarter-by-quarter analysis demonstrated that the major signals (nausea, vomiting, constipation, urinary retention, drooling) were detectable from the first quarter (Q4 2024, n=156 cases) and stabilized by Q2 2025, with narrowing confidence intervals as cases accumulated (eFigure 4). Akathisia emerged as a signal only from Q3 2025.

Discussion

This study is, to our knowledge, the first post-marketing pharmacovigilance analysis of xanomeline-trospium to include active-comparator benchmarking, covering 1,423 FAERS cases across the initial 14 months following FDA approval. Song et al. recently confirmed gastrointestinal and urinary signals from an earlier FAERS snapshot using three detection methods,¹² but did not benchmark xanomeline-trospium against existing antipsychotics. The active-comparator analysis reported here, covering six D2 antagonists with E-value confounding quantification and polypharmacy adjustment, fills that gap. Three findings bear directly on prescribing practice.

The adverse event profile is dominated by gastrointestinal and cholinergic effects, consistent with muscarinic receptor agonism. Nausea, vomiting, constipation, and dyspepsia were the highest-volume signals, aligning with the EMERGENT trial data.⁶⁻⁸ The early onset of these events (median 0-3 days, all Weibull beta < 1) points to an initiation-phase phenomenon that likely attenuates with continued dosing. This temporal pattern supports strategies such as gradual dose titration and prophylactic antiemetics during the first week of treatment, and clinicians should counsel patients that gastrointestinal symptoms typically peak within the first few days and diminish thereafter.

The active-comparator analysis – absent from prior pharmacovigilance work – provides consistent evidence that the metabolic and neurological burden of xanomeline-trospium is mechanistically distinct from D2 antagonists. Weight gain, hyperglycemia, diabetes, metabolic syndrome, EPS, tardive dyskinesia, and hyperprolactinemia were either absent or significantly reduced in xanomeline-trospium reporting relative to all six comparators. Weight gain ROR was 0.10-0.14 versus all comparators, and EPS measures were reduced by 5- to 15-fold. The consistency across six independent comparators and the concordance with the known D2-sparing mechanism support a genuinely differentiated safety profile, though FAERS data cannot establish causality and these findings should be regarded as hypothesis-generating.

Several novel signals merit specific clinical attention. Drooling (ROR 61.0) and salivary hypersecretion

(23.8) are pharmacologically consistent with central muscarinic M1 agonism promoting salivation,¹⁹ and their co-occurrence with dry mouth (ROR 6.2) reflects the competing peripheral M3 antagonism of trospium. The polypharmacy sensitivity analysis confirmed that the drooling signal persists after excluding cases co-prescribed clozapine (a known cause of sialorrhea¹⁸), establishing this as a xanomeline-trospium-specific effect. Urinary retention (ROR 44.0) was among the strongest signals, consistent with trospium's antimuscarinic activity at the bladder detrusor muscle.²⁰ Clinicians prescribing xanomeline-trospium should assess for preexisting urological conditions and anticholinergic burden, monitor for urinary symptoms during the first week of treatment, and counsel patients about the possibility of excessive salivation.

The potential for notoriety bias warrants consideration, given the substantial media attention surrounding the first non-dopaminergic antipsychotic approval in three decades. The mechanism-specific signal profile argues against nonspecific stimulated reporting: gastrointestinal and anticholinergic events dominated while metabolic and extrapyramidal signals were absent, a pattern inconsistent with indiscriminate overreporting. The Weber effect analysis showed no reporting decay over five quarters – reports increased by approximately 34 per quarter, tracking market uptake rather than a media-driven surge. The active-comparator design provides a further safeguard, since both xanomeline-trospium and comparators are subject to the same background reporting biases within FAERS. Among HCP reporters, who are less susceptible to media influence, 73% of signals were reproduced. E-values for 46 of 56 signals exceeded 3.0, and the concordance with EMERGENT trial adverse events provides independent validation.⁶⁻⁸

Limitations

This study has limitations inherent to spontaneous reporting pharmacovigilance. Two deserve particular attention. First, FAERS disproportionality signals indicate statistical associations, not causal effects; the absence of a denominator (exposed population) precludes incidence rate calculation, and the active-comparator RORs quantify relative reporting frequency rather than relative risk. Second, confounding by indication is a persistent threat in psychiatric pharmacovigilance – 19 of 56 consensus signals were classified as disease manifestations, and although the indication-restricted sensitivity analysis (schizophrenia cases only) yielded qualitatively consistent results, residual confounding cannot be excluded.

Additional constraints include incomplete reporting (age available in only 52.8% of cases, limiting MH-adjusted precision; dose recorded in 5.3%), a modest sample size reflecting the drug's recent approval (1,423 cases over 14 months, insufficient for rare-event detection), and too few CYP2D6 inhibitor co-prescriptions (n=15) for meaningful interaction analysis (eTable 31). The short observation window also means late-onset

adverse events cannot yet be assessed.

Conclusions

The post-marketing safety profile of xanomeline-trospium matches its muscarinic mechanism: a predominantly gastrointestinal and cholinergic adverse event burden, with substantially lower metabolic and extrapyramidal reporting than D2 antagonists. Drooling and urinary retention are clinically significant signals warranting targeted monitoring during treatment initiation. Prospective cohort studies with prescription-level denominators are needed to quantify incidence rates and confirm the magnitude of the metabolic advantage suggested by these hypothesis-generating pharmacovigilance data.

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Conflict of interest: None declared.

Author contributions: HF conceived the study, designed the analysis plan, performed all analyses, and wrote the manuscript.

Ethics: This study used publicly available, de-identified data from the FDA Adverse Event Reporting System. No ethics approval was required.

Data availability: FAERS data are publicly available from the FDA. Analysis code is available at <https://github.com/hayden-farquhar/Cobenfy-FAERS> (archived at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19623168>).

Pre-registration: Open Science Framework, doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/2PWUD.

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Tables

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Xanomeline-Trospium and Active Comparator Cases in FAERS (Q4 2024-Q4 2025)

	Xanomeline- trospium	Olanzapine	Risperidone	Aripiprazole	Quetiapine	Lurasidone	Brexiprazole
Characteristic	(n=1,423)	(n=6,926)	(n=6,254)	(n=5,516)	(n=9,074)	(n=806)	(n=1,288)
Age, median (IQR), y	40 (30-51)	44 (29-60)	35 (18-59)	38 (25-52)	44 (34-59)	40 (29-56)	68 (48-84)
Age available, n (%)	752 (52.8)	5,297 (76.5)	4,071 (65.1)	3,856 (69.9)	6,830 (75.3)	461 (57.2)	903 (70.1)
Sex							
Female, n (%)	442 (31.1)	3,054 (44.1)	1,958 (31.3)	2,538 (46.0)	5,015 (55.3)	357 (44.3)	705 (54.7)
Male, n (%)	656 (46.1)	3,034 (43.8)	3,308 (52.9)	2,217 (40.2)	2,851 (31.4)	163 (20.2)	440 (34.2)
Not reported, n (%)	325 (22.8)	838 (12.1)	988 (15.8)	761 (13.8)	1,208 (13.3)	286 (35.5)	143 (11.1)
Reporter							
Healthcare professional, n (%)	673 (47.3)	4,908 (70.9)	3,563 (57.0)	3,278 (59.4)	6,124 (67.5)	356 (44.2)	750 (58.2)
Consumer/other, n (%)	385 (27.1)	925 (13.4)	952 (15.2)	1,097 (19.9)	1,208 (13.3)	277 (34.4)	234 (18.2)
US reports, n (%)	1,408 (98.9)	1,563 (22.6)	2,524 (40.4)	1,485 (26.9)	1,603 (17.7)	281 (34.9)	550 (42.7)
Outcomes							
Death, n (%)	19 (1.3)	676 (9.8)	369 (5.9)	451 (8.2)	2,234 (24.6)	29 (3.6)	344 (26.7)

Hospitalization n (%)	07 (7.5) 3,214 (46.4)	2,225 (35.6)	2,121 (38.5)	4,469 (49.3)	301 (37.3)	356 (27.6)
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Table 2. Pharmacological Consensus Disproportionality Signals for Xanomeline-Tropium (Signals Classified as Disease Manifestations Excluded; See eTable 6 for Full Classification)

Preferred Term	n	ROR (95% CI)	PRR (chi-sq)	EBGM (EB05)	IC (IC025)	E-value (CI)	Methods
Gastrointestinal							
Drooling	30	61.0 (42.3-88.0)	59.7 (1575)	54.6 (39.4)	5.84 (5.32)	121.5 (84.0)	4/4
Vomiting projectile	6	23.4 (10.7-50.9)	23.3 (96)	17.0 (8.3)	4.52 (3.41)	46.2 (21.0)	4/4
Vomiting	239	8.4 (7.3-9.7)	7.2 (1289)	7.1 (6.4)	2.84 (2.66)	16.4 (14.2)	4/4
Nausea	314	7.5 (6.7-8.6)	6.1 (1375)	6.1 (5.5)	2.60 (2.44)	14.6 (12.8)	4/4
Dyspepsia	51	7.2 (5.4-9.5)	7.0 (252)	6.8 (5.4)	2.80 (2.40)	13.9 (10.3)	4/4
Constipation	110	6.5 (5.3-7.8)	6.0 (458)	6.0 (5.1)	2.59 (2.32)	12.4 (10.1)	4/4
GERD	36	6.2 (4.5-8.7)	6.1 (145)	5.9 (4.5)	2.60 (2.13)	12.0 (8.4)	4/4
Retching	6	4.5 (2.1-9.7)	4.5 (11)	4.0 (2.0)	2.16 (1.05)	8.5 (3.6)	4/4
GI disorder	30	3.1 (2.2-4.5)	3.1 (39)	3.0 (2.2)	1.62 (1.11)	5.7 (3.8)	4/4
Abdominal discomfort	28	2.3 (1.6-3.3)	2.3 (18)	2.2 (1.6)	1.19 (0.66)	4.0 (2.6)	3/4
Hiccups	4	8.0 (3.2-20.2)	8.0 (15)	6.5 (2.8)	3.00 (1.66)	15.6 (5.8)	4/4

Urogenital/anticholinergic

Preferred Term	n	ROR (95% CI)	PRR (chi-sq)	EBGM (EB05)	IC (IC025)	E-value (CI)	Methods
Urinary retention	92	44.0 (35.5-54.5)	41.2 (3449)	39.1 (32.8)	5.32 (5.03)	87.5 (70.6)	4/4
Salivary hyper-secretion	15	23.8 (14.3-39.4)	23.5 (286)	20.2 (13.0)	4.53 (3.81)	47.0 (28.2)	4/4
Anuria	3	8.1 (2.8-23.1)	8.0 (10)	6.1 (2.3)	3.00 (1.49)	15.6 (5.1)	4/4
Dysuria	16	7.6 (4.7-12.3)	7.5 (80)	7.1 (4.6)	2.90 (2.21)	14.6 (8.7)	4/4
Dry mouth	35	6.2 (4.4-8.7)	6.1 (141)	5.9 (4.5)	2.60 (2.12)	11.9 (8.4)	4/4
Cardiovascular							
Tachycardia	22	3.9 (2.6-5.9)	3.8 (42)	3.7 (2.6)	1.94 (1.34)	7.2 (4.5)	4/4
Heart rate increased	24	3.7 (2.5-5.6)	3.7 (43)	3.6 (2.6)	1.89 (1.31)	6.9 (4.4)	4/4
Neurological							
Akathisia	7	10.4 (5.1-21.4)	10.4 (46)	8.8 (4.6)	3.37 (2.33)	20.3 (9.6)	4/4
Vision blurred	50	5.6 (4.3-7.5)	5.5 (177)	5.4 (4.2)	2.45 (2.05)	10.8 (8.0)	4/4
Hyperhidrosis	46	6.5 (4.9-8.8)	6.4 (200)	6.2 (4.9)	2.67 (2.25)	12.6 (9.2)	4/4
Tremor	23	2.6 (1.7-3.9)	2.6 (20)	2.5 (1.8)	1.37 (0.79)	4.7 (2.9)	3/4
Somnolence	32	2.6 (1.8-3.7)	2.5 (28)	2.5 (1.9)	1.35 (0.85)	4.6 (3.1)	3/4
Other							

Preferred Term	n	ROR (95% CI)	PRR (chi-sq)	EBGM (EB05)	IC (IC025)	E-value (CI)	Methods
Treatment noncompliance	35	7.0 (5.0-9.7)	6.8 (164)	6.6 (5.0)	2.76 (2.29)	13.4 (9.4)	4/4
Cold sweat	6	6.3 (2.9-13.6)	6.2 (19)	5.5 (2.7)	2.64 (1.53)	12.0 (5.2)	4/4
Sedation	12	4.7 (2.7-8.3)	4.7 (29)	4.4 (2.7)	2.23 (1.43)	8.9 (4.9)	4/4
Increased appetite	8	4.8 (2.5-9.4)	4.8 (18)	4.4 (2.4)	2.26 (1.29)	9.1 (4.3)	4/4

Table 3. Active-Comparator Reporting Odds Ratios: Xanomeline-Tropium Versus D2 Antagonists for Key Adverse Events

Preferred Term	vs Olanzapine	vs Risperidone	vs Aripiprazole	vs Quetiapine	vs Lurasidone	vs Brexpiprazole
Higher for xanomeline-tropium						
Nausea	7.20*	9.38*	6.78*	3.86*	7.74*	26.78*
Vomiting	4.40*	7.22*	6.84*	2.34*	6.74*	20.65*
Constipation	3.71*	5.86*	3.93*	2.28*	3.80*	43.29*
Dyspepsia	7.28*	6.97*	5.34*	2.89	8.61*	32.21*
Urinary retention	6.57*	6.67*	6.84*	6.75*	2.54	3.74*
Dry mouth	4.70*	6.78*	2.71*	1.69	2.54	7.30*
Vision blurred	4.47*	5.37*	3.11*	4.32*	6.56*	6.28*
Dizziness	2.33*	1.35	1.05	1.28	1.37	1.84

Preferred Term	vs Olanzapine	vs Risperidone	vs Aripiprazole	vs Quetiapine	vs Lurasidone	vs Brexpiprazole
Lower for xanomeline-trospium						
Weight increased	0.11*	0.10*	0.10*	0.10*	0.17*	0.14*
Somnolence	0.47*	0.40	0.48	0.38*	0.47	0.62
Sedation	0.33*	0.33*	0.29*	0.44	0.16*	0.44
Akathisia	0.19*	0.22*	0.12*	0.44	0.08*	0.17*
Dystonia	0.04	0.04*	0.06	0.23	0.07	0.10
Parkinsonism	0.06*	0.12	0.08*	0.07*	0.09	0.03
EPS disorder	0.07*	0.05*	0.07*	0.18	0.06*	0.08
Tardive dyskinesia	0.07	0.04	0.03	0.17	0.10	0.08

Bold with asterisk (*) = Bonferroni-significant ($p < 0.00026$). Values are reporting odds ratios (xanomeline-trospium/comparator).

Figures

Cobefny (Xanomeline-Trospium): Disproportionality Signals in FAERS

Figure 1: **Figure 1.** Forest plot of consensus disproportionality signals for xanomeline-trospium in FAERS (Q4 2024-Q4 2025). Blue circles indicate pharmacological signals; gray circles indicate disease manifestations of schizophrenia. Horizontal lines represent 95% confidence intervals on the log scale; upper confidence limits exceeding 3x the point estimate are truncated with an arrowhead. The dashed red line indicates the null (ROR = 1).

Figure 2: **Figure 2.** Active-comparator heatmap showing log₂-transformed reporting odds ratios for xanomeline-trospium versus six D2 antagonist antipsychotics across 32 prespecified preferred terms. Red indicates higher reporting for xanomeline-trospium; blue indicates lower reporting. Asterisks denote Bonferroni-significant comparisons (p < 0.00026).